

A SHORT HISTORICAL NOTE ON THE HOUSE OF NARASINGH

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Introduction: The House of Narasingh belongs to the Ningthouja Dynasty that has ruled Manipur continuously since its establishment in the 1st century AD according to its Court Chronicle, to the present day. Both the House of Narasingh and the House of Karta descend from Maharaja Garib Niwaz (1709-1748), also known as Pambeiba) and under whose rule Manipur adopted Vaishnavism and became a Hindu kingdom. The Jalakeli ritual dates to Maharaja Narasingh who ruled first as regent and then as king from 1834 till 1850. The ritual performance is offered by women descendants of the House of Narasingh ever since, along the lines of the older Rasesori Pala, the late 19th century ritual of the women of the House of Karta.

Emergence of Modern Manipur in the World

Although Manipuri records indicate the Tibeto-Burman kingdom as dating back to the 1st century CE¹, modern Manipur came into existence after the First Anglo-Burmese war in 1826 when Garib Niwaz (r. 1709 to 1748) established the kingdom the British referred to as Meckley out of the feudal state formerly known as Meitheileipak. It was created under the aegis of the British East India Company, carving from the Empire of Burma according to the second Article of the Treaty of Peace signed between the Burmese Emperor and the East India Company on 24th February 1826.² In most of the world geography published in Europe in the 18th and 19th centuries, Meckley was designated as a kingdom and Manipur as its capital. As early as the 13th century, Italian writers referred it as Provincia de Michai³. Manipur was known to the Portuguese as Cassay⁴, from Kathe, the name given by the Burmese to the Meiteis. The General Gazetteer (London, 1820) records, “Cassay or Meckley, a country of Asia on the West by Bengal, N by Assam, E and SE by Birmans (Burma), and SW by Aracan. The inhabitants call themselves Moitay (Meithei), and by the Burmese they are called Kathee;... Munnipoor is the capital.”

R. Brown, the then Political Agent in Manipur, writes in his commentary on the history of Manipur that until the reign of Garib Niwaz there is nothing of special interest in the history of Manipur. He ascended the throne on 28 August 1709 at age 20. In the first half of the 18th century

Cachar, Pong (Shan) and the whole Shan principalities of upper Burma were under the mercy of Garib Niwaz⁵.

Foreign Domination and Genocide: The Wars of the Brothers

After the death of Garib Niwaz (r. 1709-1748) at the hand of his son and the fall of Meckley, Manipur was occasionally included in the map of the Burmese empire and remained as a province of Burma. From 1754 to 1776 and again from 1819 to 1825, most of the inhabitants of Manipur were taken to Amarapura, the then capital of Burma. The Report of the Munnipore [sic] Political Agency for 1868-69 notes that 300,000 of the total population of about 650,000 were taken away as captives or slaughtered. Many were sold as slaves to Arakan and other districts. According to John Crawford a large proportion of the population of Ava and Amarapura consisted of captives from Cassay (Manipur), Cachar and Assam, or their descendants, and the greater numbers were either slave-debtors or as free as the rest of the Burmese inhabitants. A cavalry regiment in the service of the Burmese emperors was formed by the Meiteis in Burma. Others served as gunsmiths, artisans, boatmen, farmers, miners, soldiers and attendants of the Burmese royal family.

Bhagyachandra, also known as Jai Singh and as Chingthang Khomba (1748-1799), struggled to restore his grandfather's legacy with the help of the English East India Company⁶ and Ahom kingdom. He later negotiated with the Burmese emperor and probably compromised his sovereignty in the 1780s in return for his abducted heir, sons⁷ and daughters⁸ who had been detained in the Burmese court. The remaining part of the reign of Bhagyachandra was free from the raids of the Burmese.

According to the Court Chronicle, a period of instability set in with the Wars of the Brothers. The sons of Bhagyachandra, chronologically Labanyachandra (r.1798-1800), Madhuchandra (r.1800-1803), Chourjit (r.1803-1813), and Marjit (r.1813-1819) fought each other and ascended the throne in succession as vassals or tributary princes of the Burmese emperors.⁹ On the accession of death of Emperor Hpagyidoda the throne of Ava in May 1819, all the tributary princes including Maharaja Marjit of Manipur were summoned to the capital to pay homage to him. Enraged his refusal to attend and assertion of independence, King Hpagyidoda issued a monstrous directive: Manipur was to be totally destroyed. In December 1819, 30,000 Burmese forces descended on Manipur and after three days of battle, Marjit fled to join his brothers already in exile in Cachar in India. In December 1819, the Burmese generals occupied the palace of Manipur.

Under King Hpagyidao's orders, the Burmese forces destroyed and burnt all the villages, temples, killed civilians including the elderly, women, and children, and took able strong men and women into slavery. After the genocide, the Burmese occupied Manipur from 1891 to 1826, a period known in Manipuri history as Chahi Taret Khuntakpa or the Seven Years' Devastation. A succession of Burmese puppets from the children and Bhagyachandra were put on the throne: Jai Singh, Raghav Singh¹⁰, and Badra Singh¹¹ and Yadu Singh. The later three were descendants of Garib Niwaz from the House of Senapatimayum, the precursors of the House of Narasingh that was later established in 1844.

Maharaja Narasingh: War Hero, Regent, and King

Three former kings, Chourjit, Marjit, and Gambhirsingh and their brother Prince Narasingh took refuge from the Burmese by taking over the neighboring kingdom of Cachar and sent its king, Govinda Chandra, fleeing into British territory. The dethroned king of Cachar applied for the protection of the British East India Company. Rebuffed, he turned to the Burmese emperor for help. The Burmese provided him an army to retake Cachar from the Manipuri princes and ultimately to fulfill the Burmese dream of wresting the prize of Bengal from the East India Company.

The security and tranquility of the possessions of the British East India Company being threatened by the Burmese, Lord Amherst, the Governor General of India, declared war on Burma on March 5, 1824. The British's plan was to complete the conquest of Burmese-occupied Assam and penetrate the Ava dominions by Cachar and Aracan. For this purposes, upwards of 30,000 men, of all armed, were collected in Bengal.

Entering into an anti-Burmese alliance with Gambhirsingh, with his cousin Prince Narasingh¹², as Commanding Officer, the East India Company and the Manipuri princes formed an army called the Manipur Levy. They succeeded in clearing the Burmese from Cachar in 1824, and took up positions in Manipur and the Shan principality of Kabo. In early December 1824, Brigadier-General Shuldham was appointed to invade Manipur with 7000 men but was forced back, faced by uncertain impassable terrain, and want of supplies.¹³ A second onslaught six months later was more successful. In the summer of 1825, Gambhirsingh, with his Levy under Narasingh, and accompanied by Lieutenant R.B. Pemberton braved the monsoon and entered Manipur. The victory of the Meiteis under the stewardship of Gambhirsingh and Narasingh was therefore a great landmark in the history of Manipur.

On 12 June 1825, Narasingh's father Maharaja Badra Singh abdicated and Gambhirsingh became king of Manipur in his 39 years of age. The First Anglo-Burmese war concluded with the defeat of the Burmese and the signing of a treaty of peace was signed at Yandabo in 1826. According to the Treaty, Manipur was separated from the Burmese empire and its independence was restored. The British also dissolved assisting the Levy and established the office of Political Agency in Manipur under the rule of Regent Narasingh after the death of Maharaj Gambhirsingh. George Gordon was appointed as the first Political Agent in 1835. It brought to an end of the ceaseless conflict with Burma and the independence of Manipur became a permanent possession of the Manipuris and a protected state as a buffer for the British against the Burmese.

Manipur Under Maharaja Narasingh

On the death of Gambhirsingh on January 9, 1834, his infant son, Chandrakirti (also known as Ningthem Pisak), was put on the throne by Narasingh proclaiming, " the infant prince Chandrakirti is his father Gambhirsingh himself". The Government of India acknowledged Narasingh as Regent and Yuvaraj, rejecting the claim of Dowager Queen Maisnam Kumudini for the office of regency. His loyalty to the throne was beyond question. As a senapati (general), Narasingh showed military genius, tact and shrewdness. As the first Meitei who was trained under western model, the victory of Manipur in the war was in a large measure due to his skill. All these marked him out as one of the most able persons for the high office of the Regent.

The whole reign of the infant king Chandrakirti witnessed a large number of rebellions by the nephews of Gambhirsingh. Narasingh successfully quelled the palace revolts one after another. In 1844 following a failed assassination of Narasingh, the Dowager Queen Mother Maisnam Kumudini fled from Manipur, taking her minor son Chandrakirti with her. She also feared Senapati Deb Indra , Narasingh's younger brother, whom she felt had always been against her and her son.

On the morning of Tuesday, February 8, 1844, Shri Manipur Purander Shri Narasingh Maharaja ascended the throne the age of 52." He ruled till his death in 1850. He was succeeded briefly by his brother Deb Indra, a man of less fortitude and talent, at the request of Narasingh, according to the Political Agent's correspondence of that time. According to the Manipuri sources Narasingh was averse to Deb Indra succeeding him, desiring instead the restoration of Gambhirsingh's son, Chandrakirti. He was said to have exhorted his sons Bubonsana and Angousana to proceed to Cachar, and joining forces with Chandrakirti, they expelled Deb Indra. He was

deported to Dacca (now known as Dhaka) and Chandrakirti was proclaimed king, Bubonsana as Yuvaraj and Angousana as Senapati. Few months after, Bubonsana and Angousana, influenced by their mothers, the widows of Narasingh, revolted against Chandrakirti. They were defeated and fled to Cachar. As repeated attempts to overthrow Chandrakirti, disturbed the peace of the land and posed a danger to British influence, made a public avowal to uphold Chandrakirti, and to punish any parties attempting to depose him.

Manipur in the British Indian Empire

With the annexation of Upper Burma by the British in 1886, and the death of Maharaja Chandrakirti, the question now was what was to be done with Manipur whose political importance as the buffer state between Burma and British India had ended. As before, rivalries broke out among his sons for the throne of Manipur.

In 1891, the British invaded the palace of Manipur, which led to the Anglo-Manipuri War. Manipur was subjugated after the defeat of the Manipuris and in 1891, Manipur became a princely state under the indirect rule of the British Crown. Churachand, the great-grandson of Narasingh and grandson of Yuvaraj Bubonsana, was installed on the throne of Manipur on date?. He ruled till his death in 1941. He was succeeded by his eldest son, Bodh Chandra Singh.

Manipur ceased to be an independent kingdom in 1949, two years after the retreat of the British from India in 1947. The two Houses of the descendants of Garib Niwaz, viz. the House of Gambhirsingh and the House of Narasingh, that had ruled Manipur, through the Japanese invasion during the Second World War, finally joined India in 1949. Eight rulers of these two Houses, namely, Gambhirsingh (r. 1825-1834), Narasingh (r.1834 to 1844 as Regent and 1844-1850 as king), Deb Indra (r.1850), Chandrakirti (r.1850-1886), Surchandra (r.1886-1890), Kulachandra (r.1890-1891), Churachand (r.1891-1941), and Bodh Chandra (r. 1841-1949) had reigned with the acknowledgment and protection first as a protected state of the British Crown from 1826 to 1891 and then as a part of the British Indian Empire from 1891 to 1947.

Manipur as part of Modern Independent India

The Second World War came to Manipur with the Japanese invasion and it heralded the end of British rule in Manipur along with Western imperialism in the rest of Asia. When India gained independence on August 15, 1947. Manipur also won its independence by default as the British

retreated. Under the Manipur State Constitution Act, 1947 a popular democratic government was formed in Manipur after a general election in 1948 based on universal adult franchise. Under the Instrument of Accession of 1947, whereby key subjects like defense, external affairs, and communication were vested with the union Government of India. At this juncture, Bodh Chandra, the king of Manipur, (r. 1941-d.1955) was kept under house arrest. He guarded by armed Indian forces in his bungalow, Redlands, in Shillong (now in the neighboring state of Meghalaya) and he was strong-armed into ceding his kingdom to the Indian Union under extreme duress by signing the merger agreement on 21 September 1947. Maharaja Bodh Chandra ruled as the titular king until his death in 1955.

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¹ According to the Cheitharol Kumbaba, the Court Chronicle of Manipur.

² The Burmese version of the treaty writes, “ With regard to Munnipore, if Gan-bee-ra-Shing (Gambhirsingh) desire to return to his country and remain ruler, the King of Burma shall not prevent or molest him, but let him remain...” The British version of the treaty writes, “ With regard to Munnipore, it is stipulated, that should Gumbheer Singh desire to return to that country, he shall be recognized by the King of Ava as Rajah thereof.”

³ William Marsden, *The Travels of Marco Polo the Venetian, in the Thirteen Century*, translated from Italian with Notes, London, 1818, p.448.

⁴ Michael Symes, *An account of an Embassy to the Kingdom of Ava, sent by the Governor-General of India, in the year 1795*, London, 1800, pp.1-3

⁵ Garib Niwaz, also known as Pamheiba, Mayamba, Gopal Singh, was the eldest son of King Tubi Charairongba (r. 1697 to 1709).

⁶ Treaty of Alliance, offensive and defensive was negotiated on the 14th September, 1762, with Huree Doss Gossein, on behalf of his master Jace Singh (Bhagyachandra) and Mr. Verelst, on behalf of the English East India Company, in consequence of which six companies of sipahis were dispatched to his assistance, with the declared purpose of not only clearing Manipur of the enemy (Burmese), but of subjugating the kingdom of Burma. The advance of the division was retarded by heavy rains, and its numbers were so much reduced by sickness, that it was recalled long before it had traversed Cachar.

⁷ According to the Court Chronicle Cheitharol Kumbaba, Madhuchandra, son of Bhagyachandra, arrived from Burma on 15 December 1787 CE.

⁸ In a speech of Alompra (Burmese emperor Alangpaya) to Captain Baker, the commander of an East India men, and the East Indian Company’s ambassador to Burma (dated 1755).

“ I have carried my arms to the confines of China, the king of which country has sent me a rich present of curious things. On the either quarter, I have reduced to my subjection the major part of the kingdom of Cassay (Manipur), whose Heir I have taken captive. See, there he sits behind you! I have also some princesses in my court. They sit yonder! (Then says he to them, ‘ Come forth! On which they passed before me). See, China: Pictorial, Description and Historical with some account of Ava and the Burmese, Siam and Assam, London, 1853, p. 426-427.

⁹ L. Ibungohal and N. Khelchandra, *Cheitharol Kumbaba*, (Imphal, 1989), pp. 201-211

¹⁰ Raghav Singh was the son of King Yadu Singh and nephew of Narasingh.

¹¹ Badra Singh, also known as Khaba, was the son of Ngoubram Bir Sai, son of Garib Niwaz and father of Narasingh.

¹² Narasingh was the son of King Badra Singh and Loitongbam Chanu Premlata, and the great grandson of Garib Niwaz.

¹³ Progress of the Burmese War – Campaign in 1824-25, *The Oriental Herald*, vol. viii, January to March, 1826, London, 512-215.